

Environment

September 2023

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context and progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find a first outline of the baseline data collected during 2022 and the first months of 2023.

In terms of Environment, the monitoring focuses, on the one hand, on the context indicator “Climate Risk Index” and, on the other hand, on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see on the backside of this document).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Climate Risk Index

Sources

GermanWatch GLOBAL CLIMATE RISK INDEX 2021. Briefing Paper. <https://tinyurl.com/sourcegw01>

GermanWatch GLOBAL CLIMATE RISK INDEX 2020. Briefing Paper. <https://tinyurl.com/sourcegw02>

GermanWatch GLOBAL CLIMATE RISK INDEX 2019. Briefing Paper. <https://tinyurl.com/sourcegw03>

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Priority

Promoting the implementation of the WB Green Agenda by focusing on research, innovation & new technologies

Regional Indicators

Counteracting climate change and environmental degradation by exploring new opportunities	Progressing towards a Circular Economy
---	--

Legend: On track or maintaining achievement | Moderately improving, Challenges remain | Stagnating, Significant challenges | Decreasing, Major challenges | Information not available

WB Economy Indicators

Performance of the WB economy: good medium to be improved information not provided

	Western Balkans Green Agenda implemented		Counteracting climate change & environmental degradation	Circular Economy (CE) progress	
	Transition to sustainable transport	Transition in the energy sector	Disaster Risk Management	Strategic framework for CE	Initiatives & actions for CE
Albania	Public initiative in place, information on partnerships within the ecosystem not provided	Several projects in the field implemented, number of partnerships within ecosystem not specified	Thematic engage-centre not in place	Circular Economy aspects addressed	CE initiatives and actions implemented
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Public initiatives in place, a number of partnerships established	Information not provided	Information not provided	Circular Economy aspects addressed	CE initiatives and actions implemented
Kosovo*	Information not provided	Energy Strategy 2022-2031 sets targets; policies, legal frame, projects addressed	Thematic engage-centre in place	Circular Economy aspects addressed	CE initiatives and actions implemented
Montenegro	Information not provided	Information not provided	Information not provided	Circular Economy aspects addressed	CE initiatives and actions implemented
North Macedonia	Information not provided	Information not provided	Thematic engage-centre in place	Circular Economy aspects addressed	CE initiatives and actions implemented
Serbia	Public initiative and few ADRION projects in place, information on partnerships with the ecosystem not provided	Several projects in the field implemented, number of partnerships within ecosystem not specified	Thematic engage-centre in place	Circular Economy aspects addressed	CE initiatives and actions implemented

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

